

The Paradox of School Language versus Home Language in the Philippine' Mother Tongue-Based Multi-Lingual Education Classroom Context

Mark B. Galdo

mgaldo05@gmail.com

Southern Leyte State University - College of Teacher Education
San Isidro, Tomas Oppus, Southern Leyte

Geraldine A. Serdan

karlorashid@yahoo.com

Surigao State College of Technology - College of Teacher Education
Magallanes Street, Surigao City, Surigao del Norte

Submitted: 4.10.2019

Abstract

This paper attempts to compare the School Language and the Home Language of the learners. The focus of this study is to compare the similarities and differences of School language and Home language in the Philippine' Mother Tongue-Based Multi-Lingual Education Classroom Context in terms of language of instruction, language function, language treatment of errors, language complexity, and language exposure. The researchers used qualitative research method utilizing narrative inquiry. The interpretation of the data was based on the interview taken from the research participants from Southern Leyte and Surigao del Norte areas. The study used purposive sampling to select the thirty (30) individuals from School Language and Home Language that consists of teachers, parents and learners that met the criteria. There is a difference in the language characteristics of school and home language in terms of language instruction, language treatment of errors and language complexity but have similarities in terms of language function and language exposure. The education department and teachers should plan a solid foundation and good bridge of the implementation of MTB-MLE; to be more creative and innovative in their teaching strategies to ensure learning and to strengthen research on the culture-based pedagogical teaching and learning strategies.

Keywords: home language, language teaching, mother tongue, school language

INTRODUCTION

The paradox is an anomalous juxtaposition of incongruous ideas for the sake of striking exposition or unexpected insight. It functions as a method of literary composition and analysis that involves examining apparently contradictory statements and drawing conclusions either to reconcile them or to explain their presence (Rescher, 2001). The researcher used this term to look into the contradictory effects of mother tongue being used in school as language of instruction and home as a conversational language.

The language used in teaching is of crucial importance for enhancing learning. It is necessary to bridge home and school experiences by using the children's mother tongue(s) as the medium of learning and teaching in the school (Malone, 2017). This helps children to develop necessary tools and literacy skills to move forward and acquire another language, if necessary. The role of language as a medium of instruction in promoting an effective teaching and learning process is an issue that has occupied many scholars all over the world for many years (Simon, 2007).

One of these serious issues is the implementation of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education in some countries in addressing the needs of the learners in their academic development. Many studies have revealed that teaching mother tongue enhances ability to learn better compared to use of any languages (UNESCO, 2003; Skutnabb-Kangas, 2003 & Rai, 2011).

In some cases, in Asian region like Bangkok as reported by UNESCO (2012), school systems that do not use learners' own languages or respect their cultures make it extremely difficult for children to stay in school and learn. Thus, this contributes to perpetuating cycles of marginalization and discrimination. For countries, excluding substantial portions of the population from their right to good quality education can delay economic growth and perpetuate conflict and political instability.

In the Philippine context, changes in Basic Education Curriculum brought about by the new K to 12 program through Republic Act No. 10533 known as "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013". One of the features of the law is the implementation of Mother Tongue- Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) specifically in Kindergarten and from Grades 1 to 3. The implementation of this educational reform is one of the subjects taught in the classroom and as the primary medium of instruction. According to UNESCO (2007), mother tongue is a language that a person: 1) has learned first; 2) ascertains with or is recognized as a native speaker of by others; 3) recognizes best; and 4) practices most.

The MTB-MLE reform in the Philippines contains ambiguity and conflict in the language at home and school specifically on the side of the teachers and learners in dealing with the teaching and learning process. Some of the whys and wherefores are the following: learners do not understand their teacher's language and vice versa; the learning materials' pictures and cultural information are unfamiliar; and learners' own knowledge and experiences is disregarded. In view of Eslit (2017), the Department of Education in the Philippines orders specified what should be done but offered little support on teachers' training on how it should be done; specifically, on teaching and learning strategies, content and materials being used. As such, it is unclear how to implement the policy in a way that it aligns with the desired mother tongue approach of the learners at home given the lack preparation and suitable mother tongue learning materials, teaching strategies and learning content.

This prompts the researchers to compare the School Language and the Home Language of the learners. The focus of this study is to compare the similarities and differences of School language and Home language in the Philippine' MTB-MLE Classroom Context in terms of (1) *language of instruction*, (2) *language function*, (3) *language treatment of errors*, (4) *language complexity*, and (5) *language exposure*.

Literature Review

The idea that primary education is best begun in a child's mother tongue has received dedicated support in many education and linguistic circles (Malone 2007; UNESCO 2007; Benson 2004; Butzkamm 2003). Malone (2007) points out that by the time children begin school they have begun gaining confidence in their ability to communicate meaningfully in their home language.

In the Philippine educational system implemented Mother Tongue Based-Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) across the country, the language of instruction involves implementation of local mother tongues consists of nineteen (19) languages namely *Tagalog, Kapampangan, Pangasinan, Iloko, Bicol, Ybanag, Sinugbuanong Binisaya, Hiligaynon, Waray, Bahasa Sug, Maguindanaoan, Maranao, Chavacano, Ivatan, Sambal, Akianon, Kinaray-a, Yakan, and Sinurigaanon* as the language of instruction in Kindergarten to year three (K to 3), with the official languages (Filipino and English) being introduced as the language of instruction after grade three.

Both school and home language have its purposes in which we use language to communicate. Learners use language for a variety of formal and informal purposes, and specific grammatical structures and vocabulary are often used with each language function. This implies to what students do with language as they engage with content and interact with others. Functions represent the active use of language for a specific purpose. Students use language functions to express ideas, communicate with others, and show understanding of content in an academic setting which includes: compare and contrast, persuasion, asking questions, expressing likes and dislikes, cause and effect, summarizing, sequencing, predicting, agreeing/disagreeing, and greeting people/introductions (Dutro, 2002 & Butzkamm, 2003).

In teaching and learning a language, error correction is the learning activity that most people think as one of the language teacher's most essential functions (Ancker, 2000). Though providing correct forms of learner errors is one of the most popular techniques among many language teachers, the use of various types of treatment methods has been recommended as it is considered to be more effective and successful than relying upon a single technique (Muncie, 2000). Pholsward (2001), in his investigation about students' reaction to the error treatment, concluded that most students were quite relaxed and satisfied as they helped each other in a group's attempt to identify errors. In Pholsward's research, the teachers would suggest answers in guidance to students and if the students were still not responsive, the teachers would identify errors and edit them, followed by detailed explanations.

From the language learned emanates language complexity in which learners cannot grasp the language being taught for them. In this study, researcher anchored this indicator with

the language disorders or language impairments are disorders that involve the processing of linguistic information. Problems that may be experienced can involve grammar (syntax and/or morphology), semantics (meaning), or other aspects of language. These problems may be receptive (involving impaired language comprehension), expressive (involving language production), or a combination of both. Language disorders can affect both spoken and written language, and can also affect sign language; typically, all forms of language will be impaired (Van Dulm, 2002).

Languages are interdependent. Therefore, any concept knowledge the student has in his mother tongue both oral and written text of the language will transfer over to the target language (Cummins, 2012). This is something to do with the language exposure of the learners in dealing with materials that allows the learners to grasp certain concept of knowledge of the language. So that, learners in mother tongue gain a deeper understanding of language and how to use it effectively.

METHODOLOGY

In this comparative study, the researchers used qualitative research method utilizing narrative inquiry. This qualitative research method is a way of understanding and inquiring into experience through collaboration between researcher and participants, over time, in a place or series of places, and in social interaction with milieus (Clandinin & Connelly, 2000). Thus, results can be investigated in detail. The interpretation of the data was based on the interview taken from the research participants from Southern Leyte and Surigao del Norte areas. The study used purposive sampling to select the thirty (30) individuals from School Language and as well as Home Language that consists of teachers, parents and learners that met the criteria. The parameters used in comparing the School Language and Home Language in the MTB-MLE classroom context in the Philippines are the following; (1) *language of instruction*, (2) *language function* , (3) *language treatment of errors*, (4) *language complexity*, and (5) *language exposure*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparison of the School Language and Home Language in the MTB-MLE Classroom Context in the Philippines

A significant information on the language learning characteristics of the school language and home language depicted in the implementation of MTB-MLE in the Philippine classroom context. The characteristics of each language may differ in terms of language of instruction, language function , language treatment of errors, language complexity, and language exposure. Table 1 shows the comparison of the school language and home language in the MTB-MLE Classroom Context in the Philippines.

Table 1. School language and Home language in the MTB-MLE Classroom Context in the Philippines

Characteristics	School Language	Home Language
Language of Instruction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Language of Instruction (LOI) of both Southern Leyte and Surigao del Norte areas anchored on Cebuano Language - Southern Leyte used Sinugbuanong Binisaya and in Surigao del Norte used Surigaonong Binisaya. ▪ A formal language of instruction using Cebuano dialect ▪ Basis of LOI is stipulated in the curriculum guide and teacher guide in K to 12 curricula in DepEd MTB-MLE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Used a language variation of Binisaya dialect as language at home both in Southern Leyte and Surigao del Norte areas. ▪ A conversational language of instruction being utilized at home which are different from the LOI ▪ Basis of LOI is the language of the areas. ▪ Vary greatly by ethnicity, region, gender & age
Language Function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mother tongue utilized in specific academic purposes such as formal writing and reading. ▪ Applying explicit technique in teaching MTB through various games and group activities to strengthen academic interaction in the classroom ▪ Enables learners to internalize the patterns needed to express concepts, ideas, and thinking. ▪ More formal language description and formal grammar learnt 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Used in casual and social settings interaction ▪ Build a positive and healthy self-identity and stronger sense of pride in their cultural and linguistic heritage ▪ Use in interaction with the learners at home in more meaningful ways. ▪ Use language functionally, i.e., to get things done or to express himself/herself ▪ Expressing ideas and one's opinion could be transactional or self-expressive in nature
Language Treatment of Errors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Evaluating the learning activities through formative and summative test ▪ Facilitating the learners in their output making ▪ Assessing authentic performance of the learner ▪ Using foreign language like English for learners' comprehension to re-check their understanding of the words/phrases ▪ Commenting and Feedbacking on their learning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Evaluating their performance in MTB through monitoring of the child's performance ▪ Assisting in their home works/activities ▪ Teaching how to define/understand the word/sentence ▪ Repetition, encourage and correct ▪ Facilitating the child in learning the words like in surfing the net and scanning a dictionary ▪ Giving of comment and constructive feedbacks of their learning
Language Complexity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Unfamiliar words in the learning materials ▪ Translation of some words/phrases that target language to mother tongue ▪ Teachers lack vocabulary in the mother tongue language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Some words in mother tongue instruction is not usual words used at home ▪ Unfamiliar words in the learning activities ▪ Lack of vocabulary of the old terms of the mother tongue

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increasing language competence of their first language ▪ improvisation of instructional materials in mother tongue 	
Language Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Oral and Written Communication ▪ Group collaborative learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Oral communication through conversational / non-formal language

Language of instruction in school and home are related to each other but may differ in the language variation of the anchored regional dialect due to the geographical location. Both languages exposed the child in mother tongue-based instruction using the native language – Bisaya. This language instruction is implemented during the primary years of the child in grades 1 – 3. It is a formal or non-formal education, in which the children's mother tongue is used in the classroom as a bridge in learning Filipino and English. In school language, the basis of their instruction was in the learning competencies in Department of Education aligned with the first language of the learners in formal language situation/activity while in the home language, there are no competencies needed in their first language and vary on language culture of the learners, so they can freely express their idea and knowledge using their language at home in a conversational way. The language of instruction of both in school and home are comparable since they used the same language. Thus, according to the participants, there is a bridging of learning the first language in the division level. Wherein, a teacher would have to consult with the students and their parents to find out what language the child speaks at home, and to seek the cooperation of the parents in translating lessons into and creating learning materials in the child's mother tongue.

Savage (2017) pointed out that when children develop their mother tongue, they are simultaneously fostering a whole host of other essential skills, such as critical thinking and literacy skills. It is these skills that they take with them into formal education, and research tells us that any skills and concepts gained in the learner's home language don't have to be re-taught when they transfer to a second language. Parent communication with teachers where there is not a shared language but where the student speaks both home and school languages also can lead to language brokering, where students serve as translators for their home-language-only parents with the school-language-only teachers (Cummin, 2007). The use of a familiar language at home in instruction to teach children literacy is more effective than a submersion system as learners "can employ psycholinguistic guessing strategies" to learn how to read and write (Benson, 2004).

Language function serves as the output of what the learners learned in the language and how they apply the language in their day to day interaction. The language function of both school and home are different. In the context of school, the purpose of learning the mother tongue is specific and formal as stipulated in the teaching guide and curriculum guide while in the home context, the drive is to communicate easily through different media and to contribute meaningfully to society, so they can use the mother tongue language well in their real-life scenario. Both languages encourage the child in building positive outlook and stronger sense of pride in their culture and linguistic heritage. Through play and chat, which constitute easy, spontaneous use of language, the child develops language skills. Thus, by using language, the child develops language skills, i.e., he/she learns to speak' read, listen, write effectively and-

independently. School language focuses on the linguistic competence and development of the child by applying various techniques in teaching-learning process to strengthen social academic interaction inside the school through learning activities.

The use of mother tongue may contribute to language learning process in various occasions in the learning-teaching process; however, the excessive use of it may result in too much dependence on it, which is less desired outcome. On the other hand, in the study of Ranola (2016), the teaching of Mother tongue revealed advantages in teaching such as: learners were able to express their thoughts and ideas resulting to high participation in class discussions; learners become independent in their choice of expression, and the use of mother tongue facilitates in explaining the meaning of some English words. According to Tang (2002), moderate and judicious use of the mother tongue is helpful and can facilitate the learning and teaching of the target language. In various studies it has been reported that the use of L1 is used for different purposes in language classes: explaining the grammar, giving instructions, helping students/checking them, correcting the activities (Greggio & Gil, 2007; Patel & Jain, 2008). Moreover, using L1 helps maintain class discipline, build rapport and reduce social distance with students (Nation, 2003; Jingxia, 2009; Ramos, 2005). In addition, according to Yildirim and Mersinligil (2000) it arouses students' interest towards the lesson.

Language treatment of errors in Mother Tongue-based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) classroom context carefully plan for the assessment practices that will best meet the goals and needs of the programs. Hence, in the school language, teachers evaluate thoroughly the learning activities through formative and summative test. By this means, teachers can assess the learners in the acquisition of mother tongue language. While in the home language, parents are the one assisting their children in the full grasp of language in the context of their understanding at home. In this manner, there is a parent-tutoring procedure happened at home. Parents keep on repeating to their children the words/phrases of a topic in mother tongue to completely recognize the meaning of the words and its usage. Because learners need to be very comfortable with their language of instruction, it enables parents to assist with homework, participate in parent meetings, and communicate with teachers in a language in which they are comfortable with.

Ferris (2017) stated that treatment of error offers a realistic, well-reasoned account of what teachers of multilingual writers such as the mother tongue language need to know about error and how to put what they know to use. Hussain (2012) opine, it is pointing to note that teachers of language in today's teaching scenario are no more identifying themselves in the traditional motherly or fatherly role. Thus, a language teacher plays some new roles now such as the role model, service provider, neutral agent, friend, facilitator, leader, motivator, mentor, educator, and a colleague. Teacher as a feedback provider covers almost all the roles as providing feedback to learners' errors is one of the most significant one (Sultana, 2009). The challenge of the teachers in the MTB-MLE is the adaptation and development of a context-embedded assessment that can be suited

Language complexity entails the problems encountered between the school and home language. In school language, there are lots of unfamiliar words in the learning module which are difficult to translate to the target language because of the scarcity of the learning resources. In addition, teacher needs training on improvising a context-based instructional material. According to the participants, they need to have time to search and ask elders to a certain word which are very difficult to comprehend. Whereas, in the part of home language, there is a related concern also in language acquisition since most of the technical terms used in the mother tongue

instruction are new to them. Espada, Bayrante, Mocerro et al. (2017) study on MTB-MLE identified the challenges of the implementation of mother tongue such as difficulty in understanding concepts, pronouncing and using archaic terms, code switching, performing low in competitions carried out in English, and widening gap between parents and children in scaffolding process as the major challenges encountered by primary students, teachers and parents in MTBMLE.

According to Fayeke (2011), language and education are inseparable because the use of language as a medium of instruction in the teaching/learning situation goes a long way in determining the success achieved by the learner. Kosonen (2017) discusses in detail the challenges of language of instruction policy developments in Southeast Asia that the language policy choices reflect the ideologies and priorities of the respective governments. In addition, the governments face conflicting interests, and they try to find a consensus between these interests. Consequently, nondominant languages are rarely prioritised in language policies, unless cultural heritage and pluralism are considered important values, or when strategies to improve learning achievement of minority populations are explored. Mother tongue education should not become a disadvantage in accessing public services for individuals and the society. Those who received mother tongue education should not be marginalized in any institutions, and they should be provided with platforms by which they can express themselves (Sahin, 2018). There is a major attention and effort that is needed to be set in the implementation of the MTB-MLE policy in the Philippines.

Language exposure in mother tongue instruction in school and in home are diverse. Both languages used the native mother tongue, but more exposure happened at the home language based on their social interactions with their family and friends. While in the school context, formal exposure of the mother tongue applied in the classroom such as oral communication, writing essays, reading comprehension, dialoguing and role playing using their native language. The formal instructional system is, however, very different.

Williams (2014) recognize the “potential reward of mother tongue instruction is the achievement of higher outcomes by children because they are learning in a language that is familiar to them. The consolidation of the children’s mother tongue provides a foundation for the development of literacy skills and the learning” in national and international languages. With so much hinging upon children’s ability to learn to read and write, there needs to be a clear MTB-MLE outcome-based curriculum designed from the outset (at pre-primary and/or early grade levels) of their learning experience. An outcomes-based curriculum approach recognizes mother tongue instruction as essential, and this supports the literature where optimal MTB-MLE programs help increase student interest in learning and attending school, while at the same time reduce student repetition and dropout rates (see for instance MacKenzie 2009; Brown 2014; Jacob, Cheng, and Porter 2015).

Strengthening Contextualization and Localization refers to an innovative approach to learning and highlighted in the K to 12 curriculum. This Contextualized and Localized teaching and learning, or the concept of relating subject matter content to meaningful situations that are relevant to students' lives, offers one promising approach to helping students learn more effectively. The promotion of localized curricula is a way of encouraging such relevance in very different local, cultural and socio-economic contexts. It is a key component of the decentralization of education, governance and management.

The contextualization and localization of the curriculum can allow learning to become more meaningful and relevant. It supports policy formulation and standard setting for reform of the curriculum and the impact of this on teacher skills and knowledge. It will involve the use of

local materials both as the subject and object of instruction. It will also involve making the local culture an integral part of the curriculum (UNESCO, 2012).

CONCLUSION

In the Philippine' Classroom Context with the used of school language and home language in the Mother Tongue-based Multilingual Education, there is a paradox in the language characteristics in language of instruction, language treatment of errors and language complexity but some aspects which are similar in terms of language function and language exposure. The two languages have its own approaches on how it is done and expose. Learner have built a foundation of knowledge and experience through observing and interacting with peers and adults in their community. The language, knowledge and experience that children bring to school form an important foundation for their learning in the classroom. The education department and teachers should plan a solid foundation and good bridge of the implementation of MTB-MLE; to be more creative and innovative in their teaching strategies to ensure learning and to strengthen research on the culture-based pedagogical teaching and learning strategies.

References

- Ancker, W. (2000). Errors and Corrective Feedback: Updated Theory and Classroom Practice. Forum, v38 n4 p20-25 Oct 2000
- Benson, C. (2004) Do we expect too much of bilingual teachers? Bilingual teaching in developing countries. In: J. Brut-Griffler and M. M. Varghese, eds. Bilingualism and Language Pedagogy. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters Ltd., pp. 112-129.
- Best, J & Kahn, J. (1993). Educational research. Retrieved on June 23, 2013 from <http://www.getcited.org/pub/102991379>
- Boles, M. (2006). The effects of multicultural Literature in the classroom. Eastern Michigan University.
- Boylan, H. & Saxon, P. (2002). What works in remediation: Lesson from 30 Years of Research. National Center for Developmental Education
- Clandinin, D., & Connelly, F. (2000). Narrative inquiry: experience and story in qualitative research. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Connelly, F. M. & Clandinin, D. J., (2006). Narrative inquiry. In Green, J., Camilli, G. and Elmore, P (eds.), Handbook of complementary methods in education research. Pp 375-385. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Creswell, J. (1998). Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions. Thousand Okas, CA: SAGE
- Cummins, J. (1981). The role of primary language development in promoting educational success for language minority students.

Cummins, J. (2007). "Rethinking Monolingual Instructional Strategies in Multilingual Classrooms." *Canadian Journal of Applied Linguistics* 10: 221-240.

Dekker, D. et al. (2008). Initial results of the Lubuagan project. Paper presented to the First MLE Conference on February 18 – 20, 2001 at Cagayan de Oro, Mindanao.

Deyi, S.; Simon, E.; Ngcobo, S.; & Thole, A. (2007). Promoting the multilingual classroom: Why the significance of multilingualism in HE?. Paper presented at the National Foundation Conference, Conversations about Foundation, Granger Bay, 2-3 October 2007.

Dutcher, N. (2004). Promise and perils of mother tongue education. Center for Applied Linguistics, Washington, DC. USA.

Dutro, S. (2002) Rethinking English Language Instruction: An Architectural Approach, <http://www.soeds.k12.or.us/Files/Day%203%20PH%207.1%20Language%20Functions%20Final.pdf>

Eslit, E. R. (2017). Binisaya" Instruction: Facing the MTB-MLE Challenges Head-on. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321025673_Binisaya_Instruction_Facing_the_MTB-MLE_Challenges_Head-on [accessed Nov 20 2018].

Espada, J. et al. (2017), Challenges In The Implementation Of The Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education Program:A Case Study. Available From: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322273832_Janet_P_Espada_Et_Al_Challenges_In_The_Implementation_Of_The_Mother_TongueBased_Multilingual_Education_Programa_Case_Study [Accessed Dec 01 2018].

Essays, UK. (November 2013). The Treatment Of Errors In The Classroom English Language Essay. Retrieved from <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/english-language/the-treatment-of-errors-in-the-classroom-english-language-essay.php?vref=1>

Hussain, M. S.; Hussain, M. M.; Awan, M. A; Farid, A. (2012). Teachers Identity in the Modern World, and the Factors Which Shape them up Professionally and Psychologically. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research* 3(1), 93-101
Hişmanoğlu, M.(2005). Teaching English through literature. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, (1)1.

Ilambiling, J. (2011). Bringing one language to another: Multilingualism as a resource in the language classroom.

Jabak, O. (2013). Why is translation into the mother tongue more successful than a second language? Retrieved on May 2013 from <http://www.translationdirectory.com/articles/article1508.php>

Kavaliauskiene, G. (2009). Role of mother-tongue in learning English for specific purposes. *ESP World*, Issue 1 (22).

Kosonen, K. (2017). Language Policy and Education in Southeast Asia. In T. McCarty & S. May (Eds.) *Language Policy and Political Issues in Education* (pp. 477-490), Chapter 35, Vol. 1 of S. May (Ed.) *Encyclopaedia of Language and Education*, 3rd edition. New York: Springer. DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-02320-5_35-1

Lambert, W. E. (1977). The effects of bilingualism on the individual: Cognitive and sociocultural consequences. In Homby, P. A. Bilingualism. Psychological, Social and Educational Implications. New York, Academic Press.

Malone, S. (2007). Mother tongue-based multilingual education: Implications for education policy. SIL International. Unpublished. University of Zimbabwe.

Malone, S. (2007). Advocacy kit for promoting multilingual education: Including the m excluded. Bangkok, Thailand: UNESCO Asia and Pacific Regional Bureau for Education.

Pholsward, Ruja (2001). Error Treatment in the ESL Classroom Context. University of the Thai Chamber of Commerce. Bangkok, Thailand. PAC3 at. JALT.

Rescher, Nicholas (2001). Paradoxes: Their Roots, Range, and Resolution. Open Court: Chicago.

Şahin, Idris (2018). Vol. 13(9), pp. 343-353, 10 May, 2018 DOI: 10.5897/ERR2018.3485 Academic Journal

Sultana, A. (2009). Peer correction in ESL classrooms. BARC University Journal, 6(1), 11- 19.

Walter, S. L. & Dekker, D. (2011). Mother tongue instruction in Lubuagan: A case study from the Philippines. Published in International Review of Education. DOI:10.1007/s11159-011-9246-4

Williams, A., Metila, R., Pradilla, L. A., & Digo, M. M. (2014). Understanding Best Practices in Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in the Philippines. Quezon City, Philippines: Assessment, Curriculum and Technology Research Centre, University of the Philippines.

UNESCO (2007). Enhancing Learning. From Access to Success. Report of the First Experts' Meeting: Defining Areas of Action. Page 5
<http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0015/001556/155642E.pdf>

Van Dulm, O. (2002). A Psycholinguistic Approach to the Classification, Evaluation and Remediation of Language Disorder (PDF). Stellenbosch Papers in Linguistics. 34: 111–131.